

SDN/NFV-based End to End Network Slicing for 5G Multi-tenant Networks

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Abstract— The concept of network slicing opens the possibilities to address the complex requirements of multi-tenancy in 5G. To this end, SDN/NFV can act as technology enabler. This paper presents a centralised and dynamic approach for creating and provisioning network slices for virtual network operators' consumption to offer services to their end customers, focusing on an SDN wireless backhaul use case. We demonstrate our approach for dynamic end-to-end slice and service provisioning in a testbed.

Keywords—5G, Network Slicing, Multi-tenancy, SDN, NFV, wireless backhaul

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's networks rely on static, pre-defined configuration, to satisfy their customer's demands. Current network technologies have provided the means to serve different types of services through network traffic prioritization according to the needs. However, this way of managing network equipment and resources has proven inefficient, inflexible and expensive as it lacks the mechanisms to evolve constantly and adapt the allocation of resources and their configuration according to the current service and customers' requirements.

At the 5G network evolution, new emerging paradigms in networking such as Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Functions Virtualization (NFV), are seen as promising enablers of programmable networks and provide the means to overcome these shortcomings. Network slicing leverages SDN to create multiple end-to-end virtual networks over a common infrastructure. Each virtual network created is logically isolated and can be dedicated to serve different types of services with diverse requirements. Through the centralised SDN controller that has a broad network view, routing decisions can be made dynamically to satisfy diverse service demands with maximum cost-efficiency. Within a slice, the required network and cloud resources can be allocated on-demand depending on a set of QoS and SLA parameters, as well as other indicators not relevant to the customers' service but to the operators gains such as energy efficiency.

In this paper, we first describe the vision of 5G networking and explain why network slicing is a key technology to its realization. Next, we present a solution for providing network slicing based on SDN. The proposed architecture encompasses a light-weight slice management and orchestration framework that enables slicing a physical network into multiple virtual end-to-end networks. We provide examples to demonstrate how end-to-end service provisioning using SDN can be accomplished. Finally, we give an overview of a testbed that has been built for experimentation within CHARISMA project [1]. The testbed incorporates the afore-mentioned components and technologies and demonstrates multi-tenancy scenarios over a common infrastructure, showing how network operators could benefit from the latest trends in network softwarization.

II. NETWORK SLICING IN 5G

In 5G networks, it is foreseen that a physical infrastructure is sliced into multiple standalone and independent virtual networks, each one called a network slice. A network slice may consist of virtual as well as physical resources. These logical network slices can belong to different network operators running their customized services for their customers/users. This accommodation of multiple network operators on same physical infrastructure is termed as multi-tenancy where each tenant is in charge and control of its network slice and the respective services. The support for multi-tenancy in CHARISMA, aims at a dynamic environment where virtual network operators (VNOs) can be realized by utilizing virtualised slices of the underlying physical resources. Building on the (dynamically) allocated virtual resources, VNOs are able to avoid the cost and complexity of deploying and managing their own infrastructure. As an effect, VNOs' efforts and resources can focus on the provisioning of software-based services to their customers. As the time to the market for such soft component is substantially reduced, VNO's are subsequently presented with the opportunity to focus on innovative services, differentiating from competition and hence fostering rapid deployment. The virtual nature of the utilised resources brings the benefits of a more flexible,

dynamic management of resources, where allocation can closely follow demand, thus yielding a more efficient resource utilization environment. The software-based realization of VNO services fosters rapid innovation, in contrast to the slow evolution of specialised hardware components, e.g., upgrading a SW firewall against a traditional, purpose-built firewall device.

Resource Virtualization: The support of multi-tenancy requires the virtualization of compute, storage and network resources, in an end-to-end fashion including the entire 5G access network. This means that a set of hardware resources comprising the underlying infrastructure must be virtualised so as to be shared. As the infrastructure landscape of 5G becomes increasingly complex, this resource set is expected to become diverse and large across different areas of the network.

Resource Isolation: The co-existence of multiple tenants on top of the same physical infrastructure calls for the complete isolation of the allocated resources. The volume and availability of allocated resources per tenant should be affected neither by the allocation of resources to other tenants, nor by the utilization of other tenants' resources e.g., network traffic load, CPU utilization thresholds.

III. OPEN ACCESS MANAGER

A key architectural innovation to the CHARISMA project is the use of a hierarchical and distributed approach to the network architecture. That is to push out network intelligence, processing and routing towards the end-users. The CHARISMA architecture has been divided up into 4 hierarchical levels, with each active node at each level called a Converged Aggregation Level (CAL). Located at each CAL is an Intelligent Management Unit (IMU), which can host virtual networking functions (VNFs). CHARISMA inherently considers open access into its architecture, focusing on converged wireless/wireline networking, inter-operability, simplified operation, administration & management, and modularity to underpin multi-vendor support as the main requirements. These requirements facilitate the provision of open access services, and unified control and management aspects and is achieved with CHARISMA's control, management and orchestration (CMO) platform. The Open Access Manager (OAM) is part of the CMO and is responsible for exposing a unified control and management to allow Infrastructure providers (InfP) to configure network parameters and to offer tailored end-to-end network slices to Virtual Network Operators (VNOs). It exposes appropriate interfaces required for the operation, administration, and management of particular network slices for monitoring and troubleshooting towards VNOs. This fulfils an important feature of 5G that is infrastructure sharing with a centralised management system. In order to achieve the unified control and management feature, the Open Access Manager interacts with the network and cloud controller to expose the appropriate interfaces required for the physical and virtual resources. In order to enable a smooth transition towards 5G technologies and adaptation of the slicing concept, it is vital to support both SDN-enabled and non-SDN enabled physical

equipment. This is mainly because some devices in the infrastructure may include physical equipment, such as OLT and eNodeB, which do not have intrinsic virtualization or support for control/data plane separation. For the latter, the open access manager may have to directly interface with the management API exposed by those particular devices in order to offer control and management flexibility to higher layers. Figure 1 illustrates the idea.

Figure 1: Open Access Manager logical architecture

The Slice Lifecycle Manager is responsible for the creation, allocation, expiration and deletion of a network slice. The Slice and Resource repositories provide an up to date inventory of the network slices and physical resources, respectively. AuthC and AuthZ ensure required access control for appropriate functioning of the slices. The conflict resolution module resolves contention that may arise when two different VNOs try to reserve the same resources at the same time. All these above mentioned Open Access Manager modules function jointly to facilitate dynamic network slice provisioning to VNOs over the same physical infrastructure.

IV. NETWORK SLICING USING SDN

A. SDN Architecture overview

Software Defined Networking is promising a paradigm shift in networking for the 5G era, through the concepts of programmable network infrastructure and de-coupling of network control and data planes of switches. It enables simplified network management and easier introduction of new services or changes in the network. In order to enable the 5G architectural vision for unified, end-to-end software defined operation across the network and enable the introduction of new, innovative services, SDN has to transform and eventually seamlessly control, both the access and transport sections of the network.

This section presents the implementation of the network slicing concept as presented in Section II & III, extended over a wireless backhaul network, performed within CHARISMA. To implement that, we based our work on SDN and related open standards. The architectural design followed is shown in Figure 2. At the top, an NFV-based orchestrator is used to facilitate the automatic deployment of network services. For the purpose of slicing, the CMO interfaces with different network devices, using the Open Access Manager (OAM) which interacts with the SDN controller sending the respective

requests to the controller’s REST API. The controller is “translating” these requests to detailed instructions transmitted through its southbound interface, to the SDN-enabled switch. Finally, in place of a typical switch, a mmWave Point-to-Point backhaul device was engineered to become SDN compliant and through its software programmability, to provide the required network slicing service.

Figure 2: SDN Backhaul and CMO

B. Q-in-Q for slicing in wireless backhaul

As our goal was to provide transport services at the mobile backhaul, a straightforward, cost efficient and flexible way was the adoption of Carrier Ethernet services. CE 2.0 [2] for Mobile Backhaul has been widely accepted, as it addresses challenges associated with managing rapid backhaul data growth while scaling costs to new revenues [3]. Given that our backhaul is a layer 2 device, the most efficient and simplest solution to deploy network slicing was to use Q-in-Q tunnelling.

In a Carrier Ethernet network, data is transported across Point-to-Point, Multipoint-to-Multipoint and Rooted-to-Multipoint Ethernet Virtual Connections (EVCs) according to the attributes and definitions of the E-Line, E-LAN, and E-Tree Service Types defined in the CE 2.0 specifications. For the purpose of this work, we focused on E-Line service due to its simplicity. Each E-Line Service Type consists of both Port-Based and VLAN-aware services, namely, the point-to-point Ethernet Private Line (EPL) and Ethernet Virtual Private Line (EVPL) services. EVPL is a more scalable model than EPL [4] and consequently was selected for this implementation. A CE 2.0 EVPL service allows for service multiplexing and bundling, enabling the support of multiple EVCs at the User Network Interface (UNI) and mapping of more than one C-VLAN IDs per EVC.

To provide multi-tenancy in the wireless backhaul context, we defined a virtual slice of each VNO to correspond to an EVC. Each EVC is defined by an S-VLAN ID which offers the required slice isolation. The C-VLANs associated to an S-VLAN ID, represent different customers of each VNO. Furthermore each EVC can correspond to a different Service-Level Agreement, e.g. a different set of QoS parameters, as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: SLA per VNO at the backhaul network

C. Control Plane – CE 2.0 over OpenFlow

The SDN Controller acts as the network operating system, by relaying information to network equipment via southbound interfaces. Currently there are a lot of open-source SDN controllers such as OpenDaylight [5], Pox [6], Ryu [7], Floodlight [8] and ONOS [9]. We selected OpenDaylight because it delivers production-level performance, supports open, multivendor networking and has a vast community of developers and strong industry support. To communicate with switches at their southbound interface, we used OpenFlow 1.3.4 [10] which is widely supported from open-source controllers and supports Q-in-Q tunnelling. An SDN controller CE application was developed and is used to provide a subset of the CE 2.0 standards.

In order to deploy the network slices per VNO, the InfP via the Open Access Manager, sends a request to the SDN controller’s REST API, describing the switches and the ports where the services are going to be deployed as well as the number of VNOs and the C-VLANs per VNO. The backhaul switches are initially connected to the controller. The controller identifies each switch Datapath ID (DPID) and port names. Using the Link Layer Discovery Protocol (LLDP) the controller identifies the network topology. A graph traversal algorithm is being used by the SDN controller to calculate an end-to-end path between the selected network nodes, guaranteeing loop prevention. Additionally, specific flow modification messages (FLOW_MOD) are sent to the backhaul switches in order to deploy the slices by installing appropriate OpenFlow flow entries. The composition of different flows is shown in the fields of Table 1:

MATCH		INSTRUCTIONS	
IN_PORT	C-VLAN ID	PUSH S-VLAN ID	OUTPUT
IN_PORT	S-VLAN ID	POP S-VLAN ID	OUTPUT
IN_PORT	S-VLAN ID	OUTPUT	

Table 1: OpenFlow flows internal fields to configure EVPL service

Except for the ports that are defined from the Open Access Manager as UNIs and are known to the InfP in advance, all the other ports are defined from the end-to-end path algorithm and they are topology-dependant. To further elaborate how the flows provide slicing, we are going to use an example where

we define VNO 1 with customer C-VLAN 5 and VNO 2 with customers C-VLAN 6 and C-VLAN 7. Consequently, the flows installed at the OpenFlow-enabled switches are shown in Table 2:

MATCH		INSTRUCTIONS	
Flows of Service end points			
VNO 1			
IN_PORT	CE- VLAN 5	Push S-VLAN 1	OUTPUT
IN_PORT	S-VLAN 1	POP S-VLAN	OUTPUT
VNO 2			
IN_PORT	CE- VLAN 6	Push S-VLAN 2	OUTPUT
IN_PORT	S-VLAN 2	POP S-VLAN	OUTPUT
IN_PORT	CE- VLAN 7	Push S-VLAN 2	OUTPUT
IN_PORT	S-VLAN 2	POP S-VLAN	OUTPUT
Flows of Service intermediate points			
VNO 1			
IN_PORT	S-VLAN 1		OUTPUT
IN_PORT	S-VLAN 1		OUTPUT
VNO 2			
IN_PORT	S-VLAN 2		OUTPUT
IN_PORT	S-VLAN 2		OUTPUT

Table 2: OpenFlow flows internal fields to configure EVPL service for the two VNOs use case.

The switches that are at the endpoints of the backhaul network match C-VLANs and push VNO-specific S-VLAN IDs. In the opposite direction, when they receive a packet with an S-VLAN, they strip it and forward the packet to the port defined in the flow entry. The intermediate nodes which are a part of the S-VLAN domain, just match the S-VLAN ID and forward the packet to the appropriate port. The same principles apply when defining a larger number of VNOs and corresponding customers.

D. Data Plane

The architecture for enabling OpenFlow on the switching component of the backhaul device, is shown in Figure 4. According to the SDN paradigm, the Control plane of the switch is moved to the controller and an adaptation functionality is required to be installed on the device, to render it OpenFlow compatible. The OpenFlow adaptation runs on the CPU of the Network Processor (NP), while the data plane logic runs at line rate on the NP’s hardware accelerators. The adaptation functionality consists of an OpenFlow agent and an adaptation layer (Data Path Abstraction). The OpenFlow agent is device independent while the adaptation layer is a device-specific module.

- The device-independent agent enables support for OpenFlow e.g. establishes connections and handles OpenFlow messaging on backhaul switches.
- The adaptation layer abstracts the device specific functionality by conveying the OpenFlow rules in a proprietary language, which will be understood by the packet processor.

As a part of the process to enable OpenFlow at the backhaul device, mapping of the abstract OpenFlow objects to the underlying network processor architecture was necessary. The goal was to present to the upper layer (OpenFlow agent) a

compliant structure containing entities such as tables, flows, instructions, meters, ports etc., which would implement the forwarding engine. Also, in addition to data path forwarding, all necessary configuration information (number of ports, port names, port state (up/down), features such as the number of buffers etc.) is collected and reported to the controller.

Figure 4: SDN-enabled Backhaul Architecture

TESTBED

To experimentally evaluate the proposed solution, we developed a proof-of concept prototype that allows experimentation and creation of virtual slices over a common infrastructure. The testbed is a 5G end-to-end experimental facility that implements future network evolution software-defined paradigms, such as SDN and NFV, and demonstrates their strong integration with cloud and fog computing technologies. The experimental setup comprises five main parts: the core network, the backhaul network, the access network, mobile terminals connecting to the access network and distributed cloud deployments with computing, storage and networking capabilities.

Figure 5 depicts the testbed infrastructure. The access network is based on WiFi technology. A WiFi CPE is providing connectivity to VNO customers’ devices. An SDN switch is interconnecting the access network to the backhaul network. At this aggregation point we are implementing a CHARISMA Intelligent Management Unit (IMU), in which virtual network functions (VNFs) associated with the existing VNO networks are running. The backhaul part of the network is implemented using the wireless backhaul link with SDN management functionalities, described in Section IV. The core network of this testbed is composed by cloud servers dedicated to run the services offered by VNOs to their customers. The core network is another point of the infrastructure at which we have decided to implement an IMU. The implementation of the two IMUs at CAL1 and CAL3 is based on the deployment of cloud infrastructure (NFVI-PoPs) to support the implemented CHARISMA virtualized functions, aimed to provide enhanced security (security VNFs) and low latency (caching VNFs).

Figure 5: Testbed architecture

The management of the virtual slices for VNOs is done through the CHARISMA Control, Management and Orchestration (CMO) platform. The CMO is responsible for the management of the physical and virtual resources composing the slices offered to VNOs. Specifically, the CMO platform is comprised of the NFV Orchestrator responsible for the lifecycle management of network services, the VNF Manager responsible for the lifecycle management of individual VNFs, the Open Access Manager (OAM) responsible for the creation of virtual slices. To perform its work, the OAM is cooperating with the cloud and network controllers, which are responsible for the management of compute, storage and network resources in the NFVI-PoPs and the network resources outside the NFVI-PoPs respectively. Two additional components are part of the CMO, the Monitoring and Analytics and the Service Policy Management. The Monitoring and Analytics component, which is responsible for performing metrics and notification acquisition from both physical and virtual resources of the infrastructure. The Service Policy Management allows policy-based programming, automation and control of the underlying infrastructure. The services comprising the CMO are running in a cloud infrastructure deployed within the core network. Through the CMO we have created two virtual slices over the common infrastructure. One slice is assigned to each VNO A and the other to VNO B, whose customers are connected to the infrastructure through the respective WiFi CPEs. The slices comprise of network resources and cloud resources found within the two NFVI-PoPs at CAL1 and CAL3 respectively and the cloud servers running the VNOs' applications.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented a centralised and dynamic approach for network slicing. The CHARISMA Control, Management and Orchestration platform was introduced, responsible for the management of the physical and virtual resources composing each VNO slice. Then Open Access Manager was described that manages, in a unified way, the

SDN and non-SDN network devices to enable multitenancy. More specifically, the paper focused on an SDN backhaul use case, where we described an SDN architecture both for the control and data plane in order to achieve network slicing over a wireless backhaul. Finally, a 5G experimental testbed enabling the creation of end-to-end slices per tenant, extending from the Wi-Fi access CPEs to the respective VNFs of CAL3, at the Central Office, was described. The future work involves deployment of application services separately in different VNOs and evaluation of performance and resource isolation.

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